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ANNUAL REPORT ON THE INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL NEWSLETTERS PRODUCED IN THE FOURTH YEAR

Overview: One Health EJP Newsletters

The One Health EJP produces two different newsletters throughout the year, the quarterly Consortium Newsletter and the bi-annual External Newsletter. These newsletters are created and disseminated by the Communications Team at the University of Surrey. The content of the newsletters is determined by the Communications Team with input from consortium members and the Project Management Team (PMT). The content and design of each newsletter is validated by the PMT before being disseminated.

In the fourth year, the newsletters were sent out using MailChimp which allowed audiences to be monitored and updated when necessary, in accordance with the changes made to the consortium members spreadsheet (for the Consortium and External newsletters) or online subscriptions via the form on the One Health EJP website (for the External Newsletter), and complies with GDPR. The internal mailing list had 822 subscribers at the end of the fourth year with between 20-22% of these subscribers opening the Consortium Newsletter when it is issued. The External newsletter had 711 subscribers with between 43-47% of subscribers opening the External Newsletter when it is issued. Additionally, MailChimp allows the Communications Team to monitor the links clicked in each newsletter and the number of people unsubscribing from the newsletter, these metrics inform the One Health EJP's Communication Strategy which is constantly evolving. MailChimp also integrates with Google Analytics and can track the traffic to the One Health EJP website from the newsletters.

When the newsletters are disseminated, they are also published on the One Health EJP website (<https://onehealthjep.eu/newsletters/>). External newsletters are also shared from the One Health EJP's Twitter and LinkedIn accounts.

Consortium Newsletters

In 2021, the Consortium Newsletters were sent in March, June and December. These consortium newsletters are usually published quarterly, therefore each year four consortium newsletters are produced. A consortium newsletter was planned to be published in September, but as the second external newsletter was delayed from August to October (see External Newsletters), the content and mailing list would have been identical. Therefore, a decision was made not to publish the September issue of the consortium newsletter to allow the second external newsletter to be published.

These newsletters target all One Health EJP consortium members and were disseminated to PMT, Institute Representatives, Scientific Representatives, Programme Owner Representative, Programme Managers Committee members, Project Leaders, Project mailing lists, PhD students and supervisors, CCPs and stakeholders. Members were encouraged to disseminate the newsletters within their institutes. Although these newsletters were specifically targeted towards consortium members, they did not contain any confidential information and therefore could be widely disseminated. For example, they posted on the Newsletters page of the One Health EJP website.

The Consortium Newsletters followed a similar format and generally included the following sections:

- Highlights or Key Information
- Events
- Key Announcements
- Updates from Work Packages

- Updates from JRP, JIP and PhD projects
- Publications (where appropriate)
- Social media links
- News from One Health EJP stakeholders

This format was subject to change depending on the content available.

1. Consortium Newsletter – March 2021

<https://mailchi.mp/ffea6eb7d830/consortium-newsletter-march-2021>

The 'Key Information' section of this newsletter highlighted:

- The One Health EJP internal events survey and the importance of completing this for dissemination purposes.
- The One Health EJP publication policy and dissemination procedure and where it can be found.

The events section featured:

- The One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM), 9-11th June 2021
- The One Health EJP ASM Satellite Workshop, 7-8th June 2021
- The One Health EJP Summer School, 26th July – 6th August 2021
- European Public Health Week, 17th -21st May 2021

The key announcement highlighted the news of welcoming six new partners to the One Health EJP consortium from Latvia, Lithuania, Spain, Finland and Hungary, therefore merging the collaboration of now 44 partners from 22 member states.

This newsletter also highlighted the Annual Scientific Meetings. The announcement communicated key information around the One Health EJP hybrid ASM. This included event dates, links to the ASM 2021 website, link to register and deadline for early-bird registration, and finally templates created by the Communications team which can be used by consortium members to present their work at the ASM.

The visual promotional images for the ASM and ASM satellite workshop was presented so it was clear that these two events were linked. However, the Communications team also created logos for each event which allowed the audiences to be able to differentiate between the two events. A short description of the aims of the workshop was provided and a link to the ASM satellite workshop 2021 page on the OHEJP website was provided for more information.

The call to host the Annual Scientific meeting 2022 was launched, and a link for more information was provided. This link led to a group on the members area of the OHEJP website with the relevant information, application form and templates.

Updates from the Work Package 6 – Education and Training were also published in this newsletter, which included highlights from the first training event of the year- the second Continuing Professional Development module, upcoming planned training events, and funding opportunities for the Education and Training activities. A link for more information was provided, which led to individual groups on the members area of the OHEJP website with the relevant information, application form and templates for the associated activity.

A section to celebrate and highlight some of the successful outcomes from the Joint Research Projects, Joint Integrative Projects and PhD projects. Links to recently published peer-reviewed papers from the OHEJP PhD students were featured, along with links to the publication page and the One Health EJP Outcome Inventory on the OHEJP website.

An update from the Work Package 4 – Joint Integrative Projects was also published in this newsletter to highlight the One Health EJP's efforts to strengthen collaboration and avoid duplication of work. This section highlighted the news of the 7th Cogwheel workshop which took place in February, in collaboration with the Versatile Emerging infectious diseases Observatory, and the EU project MOOD.

The final sections featured how the Communication Team could offer support for hosting events, and a 'you may also be interested in' section with information about the ONE 2022 EU conference on 21st-24th June 2022. As always, the footer of the newsletter featured One Health EJP hashtag and links to the One Health EJP's website, Twitter and LinkedIn.

The MailChimp statistics for this newsletter were as follows:

Number of opens <i>number of recipients who opened the campaign.</i>	158 / 781 = 20.2%
Total number of opens <i>total number of times the campaign was opened by recipients. This counts includes multiple opens from individual recipients.</i>	928
Total number of clicks <i>total number of times links were clicked on by recipients. This counts includes multiple clicks from individual recipients.</i>	73

2. Consortium Newsletter – June 2021

<https://mailchi.mp/2895c0a0c67c/consortium-newsletter-june2021>

The 'Key Information' section of this newsletter highlighted:

- The extension of the Education and Training open calls.
- A One Health EJP Overview Presentation which can be used by all of our consortium members when presenting the One Health EJP to different audiences.
- The governance meetings recently taken place meeting with the Scientific Steering Board, Programme Owners Committee, Programme Managers Committee, Project Leaders, Stakeholders and External Scientific Advisory Committee.
- The One Health EJP Data Management plans (DMPs) available on the website.

The key announcement piece in this newsletter issue focussed on the successes and achievements of the One Health EJP hybrid ASM. It highlighted the global audience that the ASM 2021 attracted in addition to the breadth of research showcased through poster presentations, oral presentations and the One Health EJP PhD Three-Minute Thesis (3MT) competition. Gratitude towards keynote speakers, organisers and all those who attended was also communicated. This section of the newsletter emphasised the importance of cross-sectoral collaboration and highlighted the environment in the One Health approach, a pillar often neglected.

The highlights of the ASM Satellite Workshop (online) was communicated in a similar fashion, and finally an announcement informing our readers of the location of the ASM 2022 in Italy.

The newsletter also highlighted the success and initiatives of the Work Package 5 team, who met with ECDC, EFSA, FAO, OIE and WHO-Europe at the 7th Stakeholder Committee on the last day of the ASM, and also regularly provide the consortium with a document which serves as a hub of information for our consortium members, by listing activities that may be relevant to the One Health EJP, with a particular focus on the EU. The two-way collaboration between the One Health EJP stakeholders was demonstrated in the next piece of information, which informed consortium members that the One Health EJP was mentioned in a recent publication from EFSA supporting One Health Policy needs.

An important feature of this consortium newsletter was the Annual Report 2020 which was published in June on our website. The report provides a showcase of all the outcomes from the consortium in 2020.

An update from the Work Package 6 – Education and Training was also published communicating the dates of the upcoming Summer School in 2021, and a link for more information on our website.

The final sections featured a 'you may also be interested in' section with information about the ONE 2022 EU conference on 21st-24th June 2022, and the 13th European Multicolloquium of Parasitology which will feature a symposium where some of our One Health EJP projects will be presented.

As always, the footer of the newsletter featured One Health EJP hashtag and links to the One Health EJP's website, Twitter and LinkedIn.

The MailChimp statistics for this newsletter were as follows:

Number of opens number of recipients who opened the campaign	171 / 787 = 21.7%
Total number of opens total number of times the campaign was opened by recipients. This counts includes multiple opens from individual recipients.	583
Total number of clicks total number of times links were clicked on by recipients. This counts includes multiple clicks from individual recipients	126

3. Consortium Newsletter – December 2021

<https://mailchi.mp/64fd8ddf11b6/consortium-newsletter-june2021-6136278>

The 'Key Announcements' section of this newsletter highlighted the dates of the upcoming Annual Scientific Meeting in 2022, and the ASM satellite workshop. In addition, this section also promoted the call for registration for the ASM satellite workshop, and the simulation exercise.

The 'Key Information' section of this newsletter featured:

- The One Health EJP Annual Report 2020.
- The One Health EJP internal events survey and the importance of completing this for dissemination purposes.
- Version 2 of the One Health EJP Dissemination Information Pack and where it can be found.

This issue then proceeded to focus on the collaboration and dissemination efforts across the One Health EJP through 2021. The articles in the first part of this section focused on collaborative events and meetings. This section described the key successes of the One Health EJP hybrid ASM, 8th Cogwheel workshop organised by Work Package 4, the first dissemination workshop in a series, organised by Work Package 5, and finally the recent governance meetings with the Scientific Steering Board, Programme Managers Committee, Programme Owners Committee, and Stakeholders Committee providing opportunities for a two-way dialogue with presentations made on selected projects.

The articles in the second part of this section focussed on project dissemination efforts across the consortium. This section highlighted the first Project Outcome Brochure produced by the Communications team for the METASTAVA project, the One Health EJP Outcome Inventory, Data Management Plan updates, publications produced from the research and integrative projects, and the first Project end symposium organised by the COHESIVE project. It also included a reminder from the communications team who are able to offer their expertise for disseminating their project outcomes or promoting an event.

Updates from the Work Package 6 – Education and Training were also published in this newsletter, which highlighted the the training events that took place in 2021 (CPD module, Summer School, ASM satellite workshop and Integrated zoonoses workshop), and provided links to the posts written to

communicate the successes of these events. In addition, a blog post was written by the WP6 team to demonstrate the legacy that we have built through our education and training activities.

Below these training event communications, were the key updates from the One Health EJP's PhD students, which included a link to all papers produced to date, and the first article published by one of our students in the #OHEJPhdlife series, which is a social media campaign to give our readers an idea of what the day-to-day life is like for our students.

As always, the footer of the newsletter featured One Health EJP hashtag and links to the One Health EJP's website, Twitter and LinkedIn.

The MailChimp statistics for this newsletter were as follows:

Number of opens <small>number of recipients who opened the campaign</small>	177 / 794 = 21.5%
Total number of opens <small>total number of times the campaign was opened by recipients. This counts includes multiple opens from individual recipients.</small>	1024
Total number of clicks <small>total number of times links were clicked on by recipients. This counts includes multiple clicks from individual recipients</small>	70

4. Consortium Newsletter – Overview of statistics

Overall, the number of consortium members opening the newsletter is between 20-22%, which was similar to that of year 3. According to MailChimp the average number of opens for a newsletter should be between 15-25%, therefore these newsletters are performing as expected. The Communications Team would like to improve these statistics because the newsletters often contain important information for members. However, important information is also communicated in other ways to ensure it reaches the target audience.

External Newsletters

In 2021, two External Newsletters were published in February and October. The Communications Team redesigned the style and format of the newsletter to a magazine style; this approach was used to address the small number of recipients that were engaging with our messages in the previous MailChimp format. The design style and format makes the content more appealing and should enable us to engage with the OHEJP growing global audience. The new external newsletter was created in InDesign by the Communications team, and produced as a pdf which was uploaded to our website. Recipients were in receipt of a placeholder image, sent via MailChimp to enable data gathering, that lead them to the uploaded interactive pdf. It was important to address design changes with an aim to increase audience engagement particularly in this fourth year when the One Health EJP has had more scientific outcomes to disseminate.

Currently, the External Newsletter audience includes:

- The general public.
- Scientists external to the One Health EJP.
- Stakeholders.
- Individuals that have subscribed to the One Health EJP mailing list via the website.

All website visitors and social media followers can join this mailing list.

Currently there are 1351 subscribers to the newsletter (as of 15.12.21). This newsletter is also disseminated to the One Health EJP internal mailing list.

The dissemination takes place via MailChimp, with a branded image encouraging readers to click on, which is linked to the uploaded pdf on the website. Therefore, with the external newsletters, it is only possible to see the number of opens and clicks of the image, not the individual links in the newsletters (unlike the consortium newsletter where this information can be made available).

1. External Newsletter – February 2021

https://onehealthjep.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/OHEJPEXternalNewsletter_vol5_2021.pdf

The main article on the first page of this issue reported on the One Health EJP's response to the COVID-19 pandemic, and the actions of our key global stakeholders such as WHO, FAO and OIE. The side article on the first page aimed to facilitate knowledge sharing through the scientific community through increasing awareness of One Health EJP Outcome Inventory on the first page.

The second page main article highlighted the importance of effective scientific research communication, and the success of the One Health EJP's Communication and Media workshop which was organised by our partners, the Bulgarian Food Safety Agency. This was supplemented with a side article highlighting the collaboration with our stakeholders, EU-JAMRAI, to increase awareness of AMR through the AMR symbol and social media campaign.

The third page of this newsletter highlighted the expansion of the One Health EJP network through announcement of the news of a) welcoming six new partners to the One Health EJP consortium from Latvia, Lithuania, Spain, Finland and Hungary, and b) welcoming five new Stakeholders to the Stakeholder Committee – WHO-Euro, FAO, OIE, EEA and EMA.

On the third page, a 'Project Highlight' was also published to describe the recent outcome from the FULL-FORCE project, who have supplied a technological toolbox and hands-on training in SMRT sequencing. This page also communicated the One Health EJP's actions in engagement opportunities in the virtual world, and described the representation of the One Health EJP at the World One Health Congress, through a presentation from the One Health EJP's Scientific Coordinator, and new dissemination material created by the One Health EJP Communications team to present at the Partners Hub. This section also included a reminder of the upcoming Annual Scientific meeting, and encouraged readers to submit their abstract before the deadline.

Finally, on the fourth page, the importance of integration and collaboration in bringing expertise from public health, animal health and environmental health to solve complex global issues was emphasised. The One Health EJP supported our Joint research Project and Joint Integrative Project leaders by designing a survey to collate information on their activities to identify common research topics and synergies between projects, and to avoid duplication and overlapping activities.

The last part of the newsletter announced the upcoming activities in 2021 – JPIAMR Research call, the second CPD module, ASM Satellite workshop, Annual Scientific Meeting and Summer School.

The MailChimp statistics for this newsletter were as follows:

	External Mailing list	Internal Mailing list
Number of opens number of recipients who opened the campaign	287 / 617 = 46.5%	190 / 783 = 24.3%
Total number of opens total number of times the campaign was opened by recipients. This counts includes multiple opens from individual recipient	809	862
Number of links clicked	244	73

2. External Newsletter – October 2021

https://onehealthjep.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/OHEJPEXternalNewsletter_vol6_Oct2021.pdf

One of the main articles on the first page of this issue capitalised on the message we are focusing on this year – “Stronger Together”. This section focused on the One Health EJP’s Annual Scientific Meeting, and it highlighted the global audience that the ASM 2021 attracted in addition to the interdisciplinary research showcased through poster presentations, oral presentations and the One Health EJP PhD Three-Minute Thesis (3MT) competition. The article also mentions the keynote speakers who also presented on a wide variety of One Health topics. This section of the newsletter emphasised the global collaborative opportunities the ASM brings, and the importance of cross-sectoral collaboration. Finally, we informed our readers of the location of the ASM 2022 in Italy.

In this issue, we drew attention to the funding of the new COVRIN project as part of the One Health EJP’s response to the pandemic. The first page also featured the first Project Outcome Brochure created by the Communications team, created for the METASTAVA project and available on the website.

The second page main article highlighted the importance of effective scientific research communication, and the success of the One Health EJP’s Communication and Media workshop which was organised by our partners, the Bulgarian Food Safety Agency. This was supplemented with a side article highlighting the collaboration with our stakeholders, EU-JAMRAI, to increase awareness of AMR through the AMR symbol and social media campaign.

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The last section of the newsletter announced the upcoming activities in 2021 – JPIAMR Research call, the second CPD module, ASM Satellite workshop, Annual Scientific Meeting and Summer School.

The MailChimp statistics for this newsletter were as follows:

	External Mailing list	Internal Mailing list
Number of opens <small>number of recipients who opened the campaign</small>	297 / 711 =43.4%	65 / 785 = 8.3%
Total number of opens <small>total number of times the campaign was opened by recipients. This counts includes multiple opens from individual recipient</small>	656	385
Number of links clicked	116	75

3. External Newsletter – Overview of statistics

Overall, the number of readers from the external mailing list opening the newsletter is between 43-47%, which has improved on the statistics in the third year, which suggests the new and improved design is more engaging for our audiences. According to MailChimp the average number of opens for a newsletter should be between 15-25%, therefore these newsletters are performing higher than expected.

However, these statistics remain at 24% for the number of opens when sent to the internal mailing list. This is expected as those on the external mailing list have all voluntarily signed to receive this information, whereas this is not the case for the internal mailing list. The Communications Team would like to improve the internal mailing list statistics because the newsletters often contain important information for members. However, important information is also communicated in other ways to ensure it reaches the target audience.

Future Newsletters

Future consortium newsletters will be disseminated in March, June, September and December 2022. Future external newsletters will be disseminated in April-May and October-November 2022.